

The role of solid oxide fuel cells in future ship energy systems

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Abstract

With rising concerns about emissions from shipping, fuel cells are expected to take an important role in ship propulsion. In particular, solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) offer high efficiency with the possibility of combined heat and power production. In this paper, we investigate energy, cost, and emission savings on ships resulting from the use of SOFCs using an optimization-based approach. A global sensitivity analysis was used to investigate the effects of the high uncertainty of problem parameters. This setup is applied to two case studies: a cruise ship and a tanker. The results show that SOFCs could provide a reduction in ship greenhouse gas emissions by up to 34% and that when using LNG as fuel, SOFCs are the most cost-optimal solution that allows a significant reduction in GHG emissions. A wider adoption of SOFCs would also lead to a decrease of other pollutant emissions. The sensitivity analysis shows that the lifetime of the stack is the most impacting uncertain parameter, followed by fuel prices and by the investment cost of the SOFC stack. The study highlights that, in a future of stricter constraints on greenhouse gas emissions and where the SOFC technology will be fully industrialized, SOFCs will be able to play an important role in bridging shipping towards decarbonization.

Keywords

solid oxide fuel cells — low carbon shipping — ship energy systems — ship propulsion — multi-objective optimization — global sensitivity analysis

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of goods transported by sea has increased by more than 150% since 1990, and is still expected to grow as a consequence of global economic development. While aviation and rail transport challenge shipping for some specific trades, it is widely recognized that the economy relies heavily on shipping, and that there is no other transportation mode that can compete in terms of costs, operational flexibility, requirements of infrastructure, and reliability [80].

Despite its beneficial effect on economic development, shipping is an important source of harm for humans and for the environment because of its pollutant emissions. It is estimated that approximately 70% of the emissions from shipping are emitted within 400 km of land, making shipping a relevant environmental concern not only for coastal areas [18].

Most of the attention has historically focused on three major pollutants: nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur oxides (SO_x) and particulate matter (PM). In more recent years, however, as a consequence of the increased awareness at a global level, CO₂ emissions from shipping have become more important on the agenda of maritime stakeholders.

1.2 Shipping and global warming

Shipping is estimated to contribute to between 2-3% of global CO₂ emissions [71]. If the shipping sector was a country, it would be the seventh largest global contributor to anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, between Japan and Germany [62].

As a consequence of international pressure, the International Maritime Organization (IMO, the body of the UN that regulates international shipping) has addressed the issue of reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from shipping. In 2013 the Energy efficiency design index (EEDI) and the Ship energy efficiency management plan (SEEMP) were introduced with the aim of increasing the efficiency in ship design and operation, respectively [48]. While these measures represented a step forward for a reduction of CO₂ emissions from shipping, their effectiveness was quickly criticized by experts in the field, as they were deemed inaccurate and weak [71, 41].

More recently, however, efforts further intensified. In 2018 the IMO officially adopted an initial strategy aiming at reducing GHG emissions from shipping by 50%, compared to 2008 levels, by 2050, and to work towards a complete decarbonization by the end of the century [49].

Researchers have been working on making ships more energy efficient since long before IMO regulations, often in relationship with increases in oil prices. Traditionally, research focused on hull and propeller lines [47, 44], but in recent years researchers started to investigate a wider set of options for reducing fuel consumption and, hence, carbon emissions [39].

Operational solutions are generally characterized by low initial costs, but also by a relatively limited potential in fuel savings. Operational solutions have a potential for reducing GHG emissions lower than 10%, apart from case of lowering the speed (which, however, has wider implications such as the

increase in fixed and inventory costs) [48].

Design solutions show a relatively higher potential, but still not definite solution to the problem. Waste heat recovery, despite the impressive volume of research produced in this field [53], was estimated to have a potential for reducing emissions of up to only 8% [48]. Even in the case of solutions with higher maximum potential, such as air lubrication and wind propulsion, it should be noted that the estimated benefits are much dependent on the ship type and route, and only in few cases the upper-boundary of the range is considered to be achievable.

Among more impacting solutions, battery-powered ships have become a reality in recent years; most applications are seen in hybrid systems, for peak-shaving [86, 30], with expected savings of up to 20% with, however, only few cases of full battery-powered vessels [51]. Unfortunately, even assuming a further increase in battery performance and a decrease in price, batteries are still seen as a solution for short- to medium-range shipping, but not for intercontinental trade.

1.3 The potential of fuel cells

In this context, there has recently been a rising interest in the use of fuel cells for marine propulsion.

Fuel cells provide generally very favourable conditions from an environmental perspective. They operate with virtually no direct pollutant emissions, even when carbon-based fuels are used. They show a high conversion efficiency, particularly at medium-low load, which is where ships are most often operated during their lifetime [7], and they are highly modular, making them effective almost regardless of the installed size.

Fuel cells are generally classified as either low- or high-temperature fuel cells. Among low-temperature fuel cells, proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC) are efficient (up to 60% gross efficiency, [82]), relatively compact, and behave well in dynamic conditions, making them a potentially very promising candidate for transportation, where they have been successfully tested for applications on cars, buses, and on ships [35]. Their main limitation lies in the lack of fuel flexibility: PEMFC can only be run on hydrogen, and if other fuels are used they need to be first converted to hydrogen; the PEMFC catalyst is very prone to poisoning, and hence requires high-purity hydrogen. This requirement is particularly challenging for long-distance operations, as storing large quantities of pure hydrogen is a non-trivial challenge. In these regards, [81] estimated that, for voyage times above approximately 100 h, the use of PEMFCs for ship propulsion becomes difficult because of their need to run on pure hydrogen.

High-temperature fuel cells can use different catalysts as a consequence of the higher operational temperature. In these conditions, CO₂ and CO molecules are no longer poisoning, and CO can even act as a potential fuel. Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) in particular offer a high fuel flexibility for various gases and liquids, e.g., methane, ethanol, methanol, propane, LPG, diesel, DME, ammonia, and more. More importantly,

SOFCS have demonstrated their high efficiency, high availability and reliability, and good durability. State-of-the-art SOFC systems provide an electrical efficiency of around 60% and a CHP system efficiency up to 85-90% [34]. SOFC-GT hybrid system can even achieve electrical efficiencies of as high as 70% [13]. Although lifetime is also considered an issue for SOFCs, system duration of 40 000 hours are a reasonable objective for SOFC technology [78], and a runtime record of SOFC systems of 10-year continuous operation has been recorded [73].

SOFCS can therefore be identified as the most potential fuel cell technology for medium to long distance ship applications. However, due to the slow start-up and load shifting, SOFCs are expected to handle base loads of thermal and electric energy demand, hence built within a hybrid system where other components (engines, PEMFCs, batteries) take care of the dynamic behavior of the demand.

1.4 Research and development of SOFCs in shipping

Despite being more the exception than the rule, there are documented cases of fuel cells being used in ship energy systems.

Most of the working examples are related to the use of PEMFCs, as a consequence of the higher maturity of the technology. PEMFCs have been successfully used on submarines [69] and tested for long periods on a passenger ferry [87]. A more thorough review of these systems on board ships can be found in [81].

In general, the advantages in terms of low noise and vibrations have historically made naval applications to be among the first to be tested. In these regards, the US Navy successfully tested the use of SOFCs for the propulsion of torpedo boats in slow-cruising mode [33], while a steam turbine is used to power the propeller during the high-speed mode. While this application has limited interest for the broader market of merchant ships, it still provides a convincing validation for the fact that SOFCs can withstand the challenges of the maritime environment [32, 31], and that they can be used successfully also in applications with tight limitations in volume and weight.

In addition to their use in naval applications, SOFCs have been often suggested for use as auxiliary power units (APU) [22]. Fuel cells, working at high efficiency over a wide range of loads and directly generating electric energy, are particularly suitable for this application, and the interest in SOFCs is mostly related to the ability of these systems to use a wide range of fuels.

Many of the cases cited in literature refer to the use of SOFCs in combination with an external reformer fuelled with Diesel, something which would make the system easy to adapt to current ship energy systems. These systems can achieve up to 55% [75, 24] electrical efficiency, with the additional potential for providing high-temperature heat, resulting in a net fuel consumption reduction of close to 50%. These types

of systems were also tested in experimental conditions (as opposed to modelling studies), with promising results [59].

In addition to Diesel-powered units, other arrangements for SOFC-based APUs were proposed, such as the use of methanol [65], considered a promising alternative to conventional fuels, and in combination with solar panels and electrolyzers, with the aim of only using the SOFC in port when the main engines are not in operation [63].

Despite the beneficial effects on fuel consumption, the use of SOFCs for auxiliary power generation can only achieve limited results. In most ships propulsion constitutes the largest part of the energy demand (see, for instance, [3], where propulsion is documented to represent 70% of the energy demand for a chemical tanker, or [76] and [10], where this contribution is estimated between 76% and 88% for fishing vessels). Engines used for propulsion have high operational efficiency (large two-stroke engines can reach 55% efficiency), and benefits are expected to be lower when compared to the substitution of auxiliary engines. Nevertheless, SOFCs have several advantages when compared to low-speed Diesel engines:

- They have no direct emissions of NO_x and PM.
- They maintain the high conversion efficiency over a very wide range of operations.
- The modular nature improves the redundancy of a hypothetical SOFC-powered system: having a system powered by ten 1 MW cells instead of one 10 MW Diesel engine makes it inherently safer.
- The direct generation of DC electricity from the SOFC allows high freedom in the regulation of rotating machines such as compressors, pumps, and propellers.
- When operated on natural gas, they do not have problems of methane slip, which was shown to have the potential of completely offsetting the benefits of using a low-carbon fuel [12].

Several researchers have hence investigated the potential benefits and challenges of a ship design where the SOFC provides most, if not all, of the on board power demand. The system proposed by [19] relies on Diesel engines for the main propulsion system, while recurring to SOFCs for low speed (and, hence, low power) operations. While the majority of the fuel savings achieved in the work of [19] are a consequence of the reduction in the speed of the ship, the use of SOFCs provides additional benefit to the system's operations. Similarly, in the work proposed by [2], the largest share of the energy demand is still provided by two-stroke dual-fuel Diesel engines, but a GT-SOFC hybrid unit is connected to the same switchboard in a full-electric system, and can hence contribute to the ship's energy demand for both hotel load and propulsion. The high efficiency of the system makes it suitable for fulfilling EEDI regulations even for phase 4, related to ships built after 2040. The hybrid GT-SOFC system was also proposed by [25] and [40] for naval applications. These

systems have a very high theoretical efficiency of up to 70%, but are still not available commercially.

The low power density of SOFCs is often considered as a major obstacle to a more widespread adoption of these systems in transportation. While PEMFCs have power densities comparable to Diesel engines, most of the SOFCs available today on the market have a relatively low power-to-weight and power-to-volume ratio. Even though volume- and weight-related constraints are not as strict for ships as they are for cars, buses and planes, it is still true that any extra volume taken the ship's power plant cannot be used for transporting cargo. In the work of [19] the design of the proposed power system also included drawings of the system layout, thus showing the feasibility of the system from this perspective. This limitation is, however, rarely addressed in scientific literature.

1.5 Gap and aim

As shown in the review of existing literature and developments in the application of SOFC systems to ships, the following gaps in scientific literature were identified and addressed in this paper:

- Design of the full power plant of a ship where the SOFC takes the largest share of the onboard energy conversion. All the studies mentioned in available academic literature focus on the use of SOFCs as APUs, or at most as the minor element of a hybrid system mostly based on Diesel engines.
- Design of SOFC-driven ship power plants based on optimization principles. All papers identified in scientific literature base the decision of the system topology, and particularly of the size of the SOFC, on heuristics rather than on an optimization of the system.
- Design of SOFC-drive ship power plants based on process integration principles. Of the studies available in literature, only the work [19] includes the heat demand.
- Optimization-based studies on ship energy systems rarely include an analysis of the sensitivity of the results on the problem assumptions.

As a consequence of the gaps in scientific literature identified above, the aim of this work is that of investigating the challenges of designing a ship's power plant based on SOFCs for its largest part. Compared to the previous literature on the subject, this paper aims at:

- Performing an optimization of the system in terms of the types of components installed, and their size, instead of simply providing a feasible design with respect to its economic and environmental performance.
- Including all energy demands (propulsion, auxiliary electricity, heat).
- Including the influence of known limitations on SOFC-based designs, such as the limited dynamic abilities of

SOFCs and their low power-to-weight and power-to-volume ratios.

- Performing a global, two-stage sensitivity analysis of the results of the optimization.

The research that is presented in this paper is part of a broader project, "Optimal Design and Control of Cruise Ship Energy Systems" (ODeS aCCSES). The project, funded within the H2020 funding program, aimed at investigating methods and technologies for reducing the environmental impact of cruise ships focusing on the use of optimization techniques for the design of the ship energy system. Among its main results, the project (concluded in January 2019) identified high temperature fuel cells as one of the most promising solutions for future efficient and low-impact energy systems [4].

2. Method

This paper aims at investigating the potential for the integration of SOFCs in ship energy systems. The method proposed to answer this question is divided in two parts:

1. Multi-objective optimization of a generic ship energy system, with the SOFC included among the possible alternative energy conversion technologies that can be selected by the optimizer (see Section 2.1).
2. Sensitivity analysis of the optimization problem (2.2).

2.1 Optimization of the ship energy system

In this paper, the optimization of the system is based on the superstructure described in Figure 1.

The SOFC is the core of the system, and it can generate both electrical and thermal energy. Electric power can also be generated by medium-speed and high-speed gas and Diesel engines (MS-GE, HS-GE, MS-DE, HS-DE). All of them can be associated with a waste heat recovery (WHR) system for providing heat (both high temperature (HT) and low temperature (LT) heat) to the onboard auxiliary demand. In addition, Diesel and gas boilers and heat pumps are included as additional means for fulfilling the heat demand.

While the overall superstructure is pre-defined, the sizes of its different units are not fixed and should be defined based on the characteristics of the specific case the system is applied to.

For this reason, in this paper the problem of the sizing of the system is approached as a MILP problem and solved using the OSMOSE framework, specifically developed for the solution of MILP-based energy integration problems [85]. The size of each component of the power plant (fuel cell, Diesel engines, boilers, etc.) are the decision variables of interest for the problem. The energy and mass streams for each component at each time step also appear in the optimization as decision variables. The MILP approach was selected based on the high reliability and speed of available solvers. The proposed system and optimization are then applied to two case studies, described more in detail in Section 3.1.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the proposed ship energy system.

Starting from the premise that shipping will need to further reduce its impact on the environment in the future, in the maritime business, as in many other industries, investment decisions are always taken with the cost dimension in mind. For this reason in this study the concept of multi-objective optimization (MOO) was used, where the two, competing objectives are defined in Equation 1,

$$f_{obj,1} = m_{GHG} \quad f_{obj,2} = C_{op} + C_{inv,ann} \quad (1)$$

where the operational cost (C_{op}), the annualized investment cost ($C_{inv,ann}$) and the yearly GHG emissions (m_{GHG}) are defined in equations 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

$$C_{op} = \sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} \sum_{t \in \mathbb{T}} f'_{u,t} (c_{fuel} + c_{CO_2} EF_{CO_2}) \dot{E}_{fuel,u}^{max} \Delta t \xi_t + c_{LV} \sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} f_u \tilde{p}_u \dot{E}_{size,u}^{max} + c_{LW} \sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} f_u \bar{p}_u \dot{E}_{size,u}^{max} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{inv,ann} = \sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} \frac{f_u c_u^{inv,var} \dot{E}_{size,u}^{max}}{F_u^{ann}} \quad (3)$$

$$m_{GHG} = \sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} \sum_{t \in \mathbb{T}} (EF_{CO_2} + GHG_{CH_4}^{eq} EF_{CH_4}) \cdot f'_{u,t} \dot{E}_{el,u}^{max} \Delta t \xi_t \quad (4)$$

where the problem parameters: the fuel cost (c_{fuel}), the carbon tax rate (c_{CO_2}), the maximum fuel consumption of each utility u ($\dot{E}_{fuel,u}^{max}$), the duration of each time step (Δt), the number of occurrences of each time step during the year of reference (ξ_t ,

see later in the text for more details), the variable (i.e. size-dependent) investment cost of each utility ($c_u^{inv,var}$), the maximum energy/material flow used for sizing purposes of each utility u ($\dot{E}_{size,u}^{max}$), the specific cost of lost volume (c_{LV}) and lost weight (c_{LW}), and the power density of each conversion unit (power-to-volume \tilde{p}_u and power-to-weight \bar{p}_u). The GHG emissions are calculated based on emission factors for CO_2 and CH_4 emissions, where the latter are converted to equivalent CO_2 emissions using a conversion factor ($GHG_{CH_4}^{eq}$) of 28 [58] for a 100 years horizon. The annualization factor (F_u^{ann}) is defined in Eq. 5 and is a function of the lifetime of each utility (N_u^y) and of the interest rate (i). \mathbb{U} and \mathbb{T} represent the set of utilities and of time steps included in the problem, respectively.

$$F_u^{ann} = \frac{(i+1)^{N_u^y} - 1}{i(1+i)^{N_u^y}} \quad (5)$$

It should be noted that, compared to common expressions for the evaluation of operational costs, Equation 2 also includes a contribution coming from the cost of lost volume and weight. This is due to the fact that, in transport applications, the total volume and weight of the system are often limited resources, that need to be used for other purposes. To take this into account, the second and third terms of Equation 2 attribute a specific cost to the lost volume and weight, which are multiplied to an estimation of the total volume/weight of the power plant.

The problem variables to be optimized are: the load of

each utility u at each time step t with respect to its maximum installed power ($f'(u,t)$, ranges between 0 and 1); the sizing of each utility with respect to its maximum installed power ($f(u)$, also ranges between 0 and 1); the on-off decision of each utility for each time step ($y'(u,t)$, binary); and the installation decision for each utility ($y(u)$, also binary). The aforementioned variables are related by the following constraints:

$$f'_{u,t} \leq f_u \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, u \in \mathbb{U} \quad (6)$$

$$f'_{u,t} \leq y'_{u,t} \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, u \in \mathbb{U} \quad (7)$$

$$y'_{u,t} \leq y_u \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, u \in \mathbb{U} \quad (8)$$

where Equation 6 represents the fact that a utility cannot operate at a higher power than the maximum installed size, Equation 7 that a utility can only have a non-zero load if it is turned on, and Equation 8 that a utility can only be used if it is installed.

To take into account the fact that some units cannot be freely operated in the whole 0% to 100% range, an additional constraint is added to take this aspect into account (see Eq. 9). The constraint on the lower boundary needs to depend also on the time-wise activation variable, which makes it nonlinear. The equation is linearized through the introduction of a dummy variable.

$$y'_{u,t} f_u \lambda_u^{\min} \leq f'_{u,t} \leq f_u \lambda_u^{\max} \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, \forall u \in \mathbb{U} \quad (9)$$

One special constraint has to be defined for the SOFC in order to account for its poor dynamic properties, and more particularly for its very long start-up time. This was accounted in this work by assuming that the SOFC, if installed, has to be constantly kept running above its minimum load. This is implemented using equation 10:

$$y_{\text{SOFC}} = y'_{\text{SOFC},t} \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T} \quad (10)$$

The optimization problem is further constrained by the fact that energy and material balances must be respected at all times:

$$\sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} f'_{u,t} \dot{E}_{l,u}^{\max} + \sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \dot{E}_{l,p,t} = 0 \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, l \in \mathbb{L} \quad (11)$$

where $\dot{E}_{l,u}^{\max}$ represents the maximum value of the net energy/material flow l for unit u , and $\dot{E}_{l,p,t}$ represents the energy/material flow l at time step t of the process p , typically representing the energy demand of the system.

The case of heat is treated differently, in order to simultaneously account for the first and second law of thermodynamics, by using the concept of heat cascade [45]:

$$\sum_{u \in \mathbb{U}} f'_{u,t} \dot{Q}_{k,u}^{\max} + \sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \dot{Q}_{k,p,t} + R_{k+1} - R_k = 0 \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{T}, k \in \mathbb{K} \quad (12)$$

with:

$$R_k \leq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{K} \quad (13)$$

$$R_1 = 0, R_{N_{k+1}} = 0 \quad (14)$$

where the R_k represents the energy cascaded from the temperature interval k to the lower temperature intervals, and \mathbb{K} represents the set of temperature intervals of the heat cascade. $\dot{Q}_{k,u,t}^{\max}$ is defined as the sum of the maximum contributions of all heat streams s of unit u in the temperature interval k and $\dot{Q}_{k,p,t}$ as the sum of the contributions of all heat streams s of process p in temperature interval k at time step t :

$$\dot{Q}_{k,u}^{\max} = \sum_{s \in \mathbb{S}_u} \dot{Q}_{k,s,u}^{\max} \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{k,p,t} = \sum_{s \in \mathbb{S}_p} \dot{Q}_{k,s,p,t} \quad (16)$$

It should be noted that the heat cascade as defined in Equation 12 is valid only for all units that are allowed to exchange heat with each other. Depending on the specific case, some units might not be in conditions of directly exchanging heat (e.g. because of logistic, economic, or safety constraints). In this case, one heat cascade is defined for each group of units that are allowed to exchange heat with each other.

To accurately represent variability of the demand while avoiding excessive computational burden on the solver, the concept of typical periods was used to model the energy demand and the ambient conditions of the system [26]. The notion of typical periods is based on the assumption that the yearly demand of a generic energy system can be represented by a limited set of periods, where the term period can refer to a day, a week, or a voyage, defined by a sequence of time steps. The problem is hence defined by N_t time steps, which are sub-divided among N_{tp} typical periods. The total duration of yearly operations is then reconstructed as:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathbb{T}} \Delta t_t \xi_t = 8760 \quad (17)$$

where every Δt_t has an assigned value for ξ_t , which represents how many times during a year the corresponding typical period is expected to occur. In each problem there are only N_{tp} different values for ξ_t , and the value of ξ_t is the same for all time steps t belonging to the same typical period. A more detailed description of the theory behind the use of typical days, and on how to calculate them, is provided in the work of [26].

In addition to the problem-level equations, each unit is defined by additional constraints. The general form of the different energy streams of a generic unit is given by Eq. 11. As energy conversion units are generally defined by the efficiency of the conversion process, in this formulation this is given by:

$$\eta_{l,u} = \frac{\dot{E}_{l,u}^{\max}}{\dot{E}_{\text{fuel},u}^{\max}} \quad (18)$$

It should be noted that Equation 18 implies that the conversion efficiency of each component is constant, regardless of the environmental or operational conditions. This relatively strong assumption, made necessary by the linearization of the problem, is common in the field of energy systems optimization [29, 84], and has limited influence on the final design. While a piece-wise linearization could help improving the accuracy of the model, it would also increase the computational requirements because of the additional binary variables.

In order to take into account the important impact of the temperature of environmental conditions on the performance of the heat pump, the coefficient of performance was calculated as shown in Eq. 19 and 20 [46], thus using the second-law efficiency of the heat pump as design parameter.

$$COP_{\text{HP,rev}} = \frac{T_{\text{HP,cond}}}{T_{\text{HP,cond}} - T_{\text{HP,evap}}} \quad (19)$$

$$COP_{\text{HP}} = \varepsilon COP_{\text{HP,rev}} \quad (20)$$

The problem definition also includes batteries as means of energy storage. These are modelled with a state variable indicating the current state of charge of the storage, that is calculated for each time step in accordance to the following definition:

$$\Delta E_{u,t} = \left(\dot{E}_u^{\max} f'_{u(\text{cha}),t} - \dot{E}_u^{\max} f'_{u(\text{dis}),t} \right) \Delta t \quad (21)$$

where the subscripts (*dis*) and (*cha*) refer to the discharge and charge processes. It should be noted that, to preserve the overall energy balance, it is here assumed that the state of charge of the energy storage must be the same at the start and at the end of each typical period. Electric energy storage in batteries also involves losses in the charging-discharging cycles. These are accounted through an electrical energy flow, representing charge/discharge losses in the battery:

$$\dot{E}_{u,t}^{\text{loss}} = \dot{E}_u^{\max} f'_{u(\text{cha}),t} \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{\text{cha}}} - 1 \right) + \dot{E}_u^{\max} f'_{u(\text{dis}),t} (1 - \eta_{\text{dis}}) \quad (22)$$

2.2 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis studies how the uncertainty in the output of a model can be attributed to different sources of uncertainty in the model input [68]. Given the uncertainty concerning most of the parameters used in the optimization process, it

is important to understand what are the most impacting parameters with regards to the existing uncertainty, or range of variation. The two-stage global sensitivity analysis (GSA) methodology, as proposed by [55] for energy system optimization, was used. It includes a first stage of parameter screening and a second stage of parameter prioritization; the reader is referred to the aforementioned publication for additional details.

The rationale for the two-stage process lies in the computationally expensive nature of the determination of the parameter prioritization using variance-based methods. As it would be too time-consuming to apply these methods directly to the full set of uncertain parameters, a first stage of parameter screening is included, based on the Morris screening [56] as improved by Campolongo et al. [14], that allows estimating a proxy for the total sensitivity index (S_T) in a computationally efficient way. Only the parameters that are considered significant based on the Morris screening are further analyzed using a more accurate, and computationally expensive, approach. In this study, this selection was made based on having a sensitivity value higher than 5% of the maximum value for at least one of the outputs of interest. Given the scope of this study, the installed power of the SOFC ($P_{\text{SOFC}}^{\text{inst}}$) and the total annualized cost (C_{tot}) were used for the selection.

$$P_{\text{SOFC}}^{\text{inst}} = f_{\text{SOFC}} \dot{E}_{\text{size,SOFC}}^{\max} \quad (23)$$

$$C_{\text{tot}} = C_{\text{inv,ann}} + C_{\text{op}} \quad (24)$$

Once a limited set of the most influential parameters is thus identified, variance-based methods for GSA can be applied. In this paper, the method originally proposed by Sobol [72] and later improved by Saltelli [67] was used. Both the Morris method and of the Sobol GSA method were implemented using the SALib Python package [37].

3. Application

3.1 Case studies

The methodology described in Section 2 for exploring the role of SOFCs in future ship energy systems was applied on two case studies, described in this section: a cruise ship (Section 3.1.1) and a chemical tanker (Section 3.1.2). The two cases were selected based on the availability of operational measurements of the energy demand, and on the preference to apply the proposed methodology on two cases with substantial differences in mission and operational profile.

3.1.1 Cruise ship

The case study for a cruise ship is based on the work presented in [6], and refers to a small cruise ship (176.9 m long, beam of 28.6 m) with a capacity of 1800 passengers operated in the Baltic Sea. The ship is equipped with several amenities and with a large system for heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC), making its auxiliary energy demand larger and more varied than that of a standard cargo vessel. The ship currently in operations is equipped with a total of eight Diesel

Figure 2. Propulsion

engines: four main engines with a power of 5760 kW each, and four auxiliary engines with a power of 2780 kW each. The heating demand is fulfilled by six heat recovery steam generators (HRSG), located on the exhaust line of the four auxiliary engines and of two of the four main propulsion engines, by a recovery system for the engine cooling waste heat, and by two oil-fired boilers. This work focuses on the case of a newly built ship of similar size and operational profile.

The energy demand is based on [6]. The heat demand is assumed to be subdivided in a low-temperature heating system operated between 40 to 60°C and used to fulfill the demand for air conditioning, and a high-temperature system using steam at 110°C that fulfills the heating demand for other on board uses, such as for the machine room or the galley. The demand, originally based on a full year of operations, was clustered into a total of five typical days, one of which being an “extreme day” for the propulsive power demand, each made of 13 variable-length time steps (see Figure 2 to 5):

- Winter ($\xi_{1-13} = 31$)
- Mid-season (C) ($\xi_{14-26} = 172$)
- Mid-season (H) ($\xi_{27-39} = 112$)
- Summer ($\xi_{40-52} = 41$)
- High propulsion demand ($\xi_{53-65} = 9$)

This is justified by the fact that the ship operates on daily cruises, and hence the operational and ambient fluctuations take place with a cycle of the same duration. The four main typical days represent normal ship operations in three different seasons (hence the difference in heat demand), while the

Figure 3. Electric power

Figure 4. High temperature heating

Figure 5. Low temperature heating

extreme day represents high-speed sailing conditions. The demand hence resulting from the clustering of the original dataset into typical days is 25.9 GWh for propulsion, 15.5 GWh for electricity, 6.6 GWh for high temperature heat demand and 8.6 GWh for low temperature heat demand.

3.1.2 Chemical tanker

The case study for a chemical tanker is a Panamax vessel with a cargo capacity of 47000 tons. The ship currently uses two 4-stroke Diesel engines rated 3,840 kW each for propulsion, both connected to a common gearbox. The gearbox is, in turn, connected to a controllable pitch propeller and to an electric generator which provides 60 Hz current to the ship. Additionally, two auxiliary engines rated 682 kW each can also provide electric power. Auxiliary heat needs are fulfilled by the HRSG or by auxiliary boilers. A more detailed analysis of the ship and its energy demand can be found in [3].

A similar approach is used as for the case of the cruise ship to reduce the number of time steps of the optimization, hence defining some "typical periods". In this case, however, the ship does not operate on a regular, daily basis, and the assumption of "typical days" would not be realistic. For this reason, for this case study the "typical day" approach was substituted by a "typical voyage" one. The summary of the demand data is provided in Table 1, which is based on the analysis of the dataset presented in [3]. The three days represent respectively a short-sea voyage (total voyage time: 78 hours), a long-sea voyage (total voyage time: 222 hours) and a high-speed, long-sea voyage (total voyage time: 222 hours, higher propulsion power demand at sea), where the latter takes the role of "design-voyage".

3.2 Problem parameters

The complete list of uncertain parameters with the respective reference and boundary values are provided in Tables 2-6, while details about the specific assumptions for each parameter are provided in subsections 3.2.1 to 3.2.8.

When not otherwise mentioned, the following assumptions were employed:

- For efficiency-related parameters, the uncertainty was assumed to be $\pm 6\%$ based on the findings of [55].
- For investment cost-related parameters, the uncertainty was assumed to be $\pm 21\%$ based on the findings of [55].
- For temperatures, the uncertainty was assumed arbitrarily to be $\pm 20\%$ of the value in $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- For lifetimes, the uncertainty was assumed arbitrarily to be ± 5 years.

In both cases, the GSA was applied to a total of 88 uncertain parameters.

3.2.1 Solid oxide fuel cell

Cost factors related to the solid oxide fuel cells were derived from [11]. The same reference was used to determine the uncertainty, which was derived as a combination of the sensitivity of the investment cost calculated as part of the sensitivity analysis in [11], and of the variations related to the expected production volume in the same study. Reference values refer to a production volume of 1000 units per year. The assumptions related to the stack lifetime are derived from [70].

The efficiency and operating temperatures of the SOFC were taken using the SOFC-based cogeneration unit by Convion [17], that is being tested in selected projects for application in the maritime industry [38]. The company reports rated electric and thermal efficiency of 0.53 and 0.27 respectively for their 58 kW unit. The lower bound (0.52) reflects the fact that the actual efficiency might be marginally lower, while the upper bound (0.60) was assumed based on the INNO-SOFC targets [8, 27]. The bounds for the thermal efficiency were arbitrarily assumed to 0.20 and 0.35 based on the variation of the electrical efficiency. Default values for the inlet and outlet temperatures of the exhaust gas were taken from Convion data.

Values for the maximum and minimum load were assumed, and are mostly related to the concept of preserving the conversion efficiency. SOFCs are known to preserve relatively well the conversion efficiency over a wide range of operations.

Finally, the reference values assumed for power density were taken from the results of the CH2P project [15]. The lower bound was assumed extrapolating the performance of the Convion module [17], while the upper bounds were assumed based on the Delphi-APU prototype [65].

3.2.2 Internal combustion engines

Gas engines were modelled based on the two cases of marine gas engines: the Rolls Royce C25:33L9A as medium

	Typical Journey 1 ($\xi_{1-7} = 40$)				Typical Journey 2 ($\xi_{8-14} = 20$)				Typical Journey 3 ($\xi_{15-21} = 5$)			
	t [h]	\dot{W}_{prop} [MW]	\dot{W}_{el} [MW]	\dot{Q} [MW]	t [h]	\dot{W}_{prop} [MW]	\dot{W}_{el} [MW]	\dot{Q} [MW]	t [h]	\dot{W}_{prop} [MW]	\dot{W}_{el} [MW]	\dot{Q} [MW]
Port	18	0.0	0.3	0.2	48	0.0	0.3	0.2	48	0.0	0.5	1.2
Man.	3	3.0	0.7	0.2	3	3.0	0.7	0.2	3	3.0	0.9	1.2
Tank. Cl.	6	5.0	0.5	1.5	6	5.0	0.5	1.5	6	7.5	0.7	1.2
Sailing	30	5.0	0.4	0.2	114	5.0	0.4	0.2	114	7.5	0.6	1.2
Man.	3	3.0	0.7	0.2	3	3.0	0.7	0.2	3	3.0	0.9	1.2
Unload.	6	0.0	1	0.2	6	0.0	1.0	0.2	6	0.0	1.8	1.2
Port	12	0.0	0.3	0.2	42	0.0	0.3	0.2	42	0.0	0.5	1.2

Table 1. Typical journeys for the tanker case study

ECU	Parameter	Unit	Ref.	LB	HB
SOFC (stack)	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	380	271	612
SOFC (system)	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	868	573	1296
SOFC (stack)	N_u^y	y	6	3	8
SOFC (system)	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
Gas Engine (MS)	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	675	529	821
Gas Engine (MS)	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
Gas Engine (HS)	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	575	451	699
Gas Engine (HS)	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
Diesel Engine (MS)	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	575	529	821
Diesel Engine (MS)	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
Diesel Engine (HS)	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	475	451	699
Diesel Engine (HS)	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
Gas Boiler	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{th}}$	54	42	66
Gas Boiler	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
Battery	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kWh}$	256	150	500
Battery	N_u^y	y	5	4	10
Heat Pump	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{th}}$	550	431	669
Heat Pump	N_u^y	y	20	15	25
El. Generator	$c_u^{inv,var}$	$\frac{EUR}{kW_{el}}$	30	24	36
El. Generator	N_u^y	y	20	15	25

Table 2. Uncertain parameters, investment cost factors

ECU	Parameter	Unit	Ref.	LB	HB
SOFC	η_{el}	-	0.530	0.520	0.650
SOFC	η_{th}	-	0.270	0.260	0.350
ICE (MS)	η_{el}	-	0.450	0.423	0.477
ICE (MS)	η_{HT}	-	0.156	0.147	0.165
ICE (MS)	η_{LT}	-	0.131	0.123	0.139
ICE (MS)	η_{eg}	-	0.263	0.247	0.279
ICE (HS)	η_{el}	-	0.400	0.376	0.424
ICE (HS)	η_{HT}	-	0.156	0.147	0.165
ICE (HS)	η_{LT}	-	0.131	0.123	0.139
ICE (HS)	η_{eg}	-	0.363	0.341	0.385
Gas Boiler	η_{th}	-	0.850	0.799	0.901
Battery	η_{el}^{ch}	-	0.926	0.870	0.982
Battery	η_{el}^{dis}	-	0.975	0.920	0.990
Heat Pump	ε	-	0.450	0.500	0.550

Table 3. Uncertain parameters, efficiency

ECU	Parameter	Unit	Ref.	LB	HB
SOFC	T_{eg}^{in}	$^{\circ}C$	220	176	264
SOFC	T_{eg}^{out}	$^{\circ}C$	40	32	48
SOFC	λ_{min}	-	0.1	0	0.2
SOFC	λ_{max}	-	0.9	0.8	1
ICE (MS)	T_{eg}^{in}	$^{\circ}C$	300	240	360
ICE (MS)	T_{eg}^{out}	$^{\circ}C$	120	96	144
ICE (HS)	T_{eg}^{in}	$^{\circ}C$	350	280	420
ICE (HS)	T_{eg}^{out}	$^{\circ}C$	120	96	144
Gas Boiler	T_{eg}^{in}	$^{\circ}C$	900	720	1080
Gas Boiler	T_{eg}^{out}	$^{\circ}C$	120	96	144
Battery	C	-	2	1.5	6
Battery	SOC^{max}	-	0.7	0.5	0.8

Table 4. Uncertain parameters, other performance-related parameters

ECU	Parameter	Unit	Ref.	LB	HB
SOFC	\bar{p}	kW/kg	0.06	0.035	0.24
SOFC	\tilde{p}	kW/m ³	5	2	16
ICE (MS)	\bar{p}	kW/kg	0.07	0.063	0.077
ICE (MS)	\tilde{p}	kW/m ³	64	57.6	70.4
ICE (HS)	\bar{p}	kW/kg	0.25	0.225	0.275
ICE (HS)	\tilde{p}	kW/m ³	195	176	215
Gas Boiler	\bar{q}	kW/kg	0.360	0.324	0.396
Gas Boiler	\tilde{q}	kW/m ³	104	94	114
Battery	\bar{e}	kWh/kg	0.08	0.072	0.088
Battery	\tilde{e}	kWh/m ³	91	81.9	100.1
Heat Pump	\bar{q}	kW/kg	0.210	0.189	0.231
Heat Pump	\tilde{q}	kW/m ³	92	83	101
El. Generator	\bar{p}	kW/kg	0.212	0.191	0.254
El. Generator	\tilde{p}	kW/m ³	126	120	151

Table 5. Uncertain parameters, specific power (weight- and volume-based)

speed gas engine, and the Mitsubishi S16R-T2 high speed

gas engine. The exhaust gas temperatures were assumed to 300°C and 350 °C, respectively, based on general knowledge related to the behaviour of these engine types. As for all other traditional components, the lifetime was assumed to 20 years. The investment cost of the MS engine was assumed based on [77], while the investment cost of the HS engine, in absence of more reliable information, was assumed to be 100 EUR/kW lower compared to the MS engine, as HS marine engines are

Parameter	Unit	Ref.	LB	HB
i	-	0.08	0.06	0.13
c_{LV}	EUR/m ³	250	20	1000
c_{LW}	EUR/kg	0.105	0.084	0.127
c_{fuel}	EUR/kWh	0.0287	0.0261	0.0536

Table 6. Uncertain parameters, other cost-related parameters

ECU	Source	CO ₂	CH ₄	GHG	NO _x
SOFC	[17]	374	0.0	374	0.0
Gas Engine (MS)	[74]	440	4.1	555	0.9
Gas Engine (HS)	[74]	495	4.9	633	0.9
Diesel Engine (MS)	[52]	513	0.0	513	2.3
Diesel Engine (HS)	[52]	577	0.0	577	2.0

Table 7. Emission factors for energy conversion units. All values are given in [g/kWh]

known to be cheaper compared to MS ones.

The electrical efficiency was assumed to vary within 6% of its reference value [55], while other efficiencies, related to the energy share wasted to the exhaust gas and to the cooling systems, were re-calculated based on energy conservation principles. An uncertainty of 10% was assumed for the power density parameters.

Engines also require the installation of an electrical generator to convert power from mechanical to electric. The efficiency of this system was assumed to 0.95, while the investment cost was assumed equal to 30 EUR/kW [79]. Power densities parameters were deduced from the generator installed on the Bergen C26:33L engine [66].

The default and uncertain parameters (apart from cost-related ones) were assumed to be the same for gas engines and Diesel engines (all shown under the category "internal combustion engines", (ICE)).

3.2.3 Gas boilers

Gas boilers are modelled using a reference value for the first-law efficiency of 0.85, based on [16] and [57]. For the sake of modelling the heat cascade, the boiler is modelled as a hot flow to be cooled from 900°C to 120°C. The specific cost was assumed to 54 EUR/kW [60]. Power density parameters were calculated based on the data from Aalborg OS boiler [43].

3.2.4 Heat pumps

In order to take into account the important impact of the temperature of the low-temperature heat source, the efficiency of the heat pumps was calculated as shown in Eq. 19 and 20, thus requiring a value for the exergy efficiency. This was assumed to be equal to 0.45 based on [36], while the lower and upper bounds were set to 0.4 and 0.55 arbitrarily. Reference values for the power density were calculated based on the Viessmann heat pump (model Vitocal HT 353.AHT147) [83]. For reference, for a heat pump operating with $T_{eva} = 303$ K and $T_{eva} = 363$ K, the calculated COP is 2.72.

3.2.5 Batteries

Batteries are generally modelled using two efficiency values: one for the charge, and one for the discharge process. The reference values are taken from [1]. With relation to costs, the reference investment cost is adapted based on [61], similarly to the bounds (based on the expectations of future price development, and on the type of information source). The reference lifetime was assumed arbitrarily, similarly to its bounds, as there is currently no well-detailed and trusted information with relation to the expected lifetime of large scale lithium-ion batteries, particularly for maritime applications. Power density parameters were calculated based on the data from Corvus Orca Energy maritime batteries [23].

3.2.6 Other cost-related parameters

The reference and bound values for the price of natural gas (C_{fuel}) were estimated based on [9]. The values for the price of MDO were based on the observation that MDO prices tend to be correlated to LNG prices, with a 1.6 factor in between [20]. This assumption was used for both reference, upper bound and lower bound values. A value of 0.08 was assumed for the interest rate (i), varying between 0.06 and 0.13 based on [42]. The cost of lost volume and the cost of lost weight were assumed based on an analysis of the cost of sea passage (in the case of the cruise ship) and of the daily charter rates (in the case of the tanker).

Discussions of implementing a market-based measure on GHG emissions have been going on for some time now, also in the maritime business. While today there is no direct cost in shipping related to GHG emissions, the sensitivity analysis should also include an evaluation of the potential impact of the implementation of this type of measures. This was included, as shown in section 2.1, in the form of a tax proportional to the emissions of carbon dioxide. The reference value (and, thus, the lower boundary) of the cost of one ton of CO₂ emitted into the atmosphere is assumed to be equal to zero, based on the current absence of a carbon tax in shipping. The upper boundary was set to 0.2 EUR/kg, based on the scenario with the largest carbon tax proposed in [64].

3.2.7 Emission factors

The analysis proposed in this paper includes three main pollutant categories: PM, GHG (thereby including also the contribution of methane slip), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). The emission factors shown in Table 7 were used to estimate the emissions resulting from the use of different energy conversion units. Emission factors for CO₂ were calculated based on the fuel used (LNG or MDO) and on the efficiency of the energy conversion unit. Emission factors for CH₄ and NO_x were retrieved from the references indicated in Table 8. A factor 28 was used to convert CH₄ emissions to CO_{2,eq} emissions [58]. Since the environmental objective is not included in the GSA, the definition of uncertain bounds for emission factors was not necessary in this study, apart from the influence of the prime mover's efficiency on CO₂ emission factors.

3.2.8 Ship demand

While basing the analysis on available past operational data is a reasonable choice, there is not certainty that the ship will be operated in this same way in the future. The ship might be sold to a different owner, employed on a different route, operated at a different speed in a different climate. For this reason, the ship demand is also considered to be subject to uncertainty. In this work, it was assumed that the uncertainty can be concentrated on two parameters for each of the demands: the mean, and the standard deviation. Based on this assumption, the demand used in each run of the sensitivity analysis, at each time step, is calculated as described in Eq. 25.

$$\dot{E}_{l,p,t}^s = \dot{E}_{l,p,t}^{\text{ref}} (\mu_{l,p}^s - \mu_{l,p}^{\text{ref}}) + (\dot{E}_{l,p,t}^{\text{ref}} - \mu_{l,p}^{\text{ref}}) \frac{\sigma_{l,p}^s}{\sigma_{l,p}^{\text{ref}}} \quad (25)$$

The s superscript refers to each optimization run of the GSA, while the specific ref superscript refers to the reference one. μ and σ represent the mean and standard deviation of each type of demand. For each of these parameters a $\pm 20\%$ uncertainty was arbitrarily assumed.

4. Results

4.1 Multi-objective optimization

The results of the MOO are shown in Figures 6 to 9. The MOO problem is implemented using the ε -constraint method [50], where the total GHG emissions of the system were constrained to decreasing values, ranging from the single-objective cost-optimal solution to the single-objective, GHG-optimal solution.

The trade-off between total costs and the reduction in GHG emissions appear clearly. In both case studies, focusing on emissions can reduce them by up to more than 30% compared to the cost optimal case, showing how a significant reduction in ship emissions can be achieved already by acting on the ship's power plant.

This reduction, however, comes at a cost. In both case studies, reducing GHG emissions by approximately 30% comes at a substantial increase in the total cost: +27% in the case of the cruise ship and +43% in the case of the tanker, with respect of the cost-optimal case. As expected, this increase is due to the largest extent to the increase in the annualized investment costs, that increase by up to 2.5 times in the cruise ship case, and almost 3.5 times in the tanker case. On the other hand, operational costs decrease, driven by the higher system efficiency, and thereby lower fuel consumption, and by the switch from MDO to LNG.

Finally, in the cruise ship case, there is a small, but still significant contribution to the total cost related to the cost of lost volume: in the Pareto-optimal scenario with the lowest GHG emissions, this figure represents approximately 6% of the total costs, and is estimated to generate a 14% increase in operating costs. In the case of the tanker, where weight

is considered as the limiting factor, this element is instead almost negligible: the difference in power density between SOFCs and internal combustion engines is, as of today, larger in terms of power-to-volume than in power-to-weight ratio.

Figure 6. Results of the multi-objective optimization: Annualized costs

Figure 7 shows how the installed size of the different components evolve when the constraint on the maximum operating costs is modified. The installation of the SOFC increases almost proportionally with the reduction of GHG emissions, due to the higher efficiency and the absence of methane slip phenomena. This is in line with the expectations: SOFCs are the technology with the highest cost per installed kW, but are also the most efficient, making them most suitable when the focus is on operational costs and emissions. It should be noted that the total installed size of the different prime movers varies remarkably between the two cases. In both ships the total installed power is dimensioned for "limit cases", such as very high speed sailing. However, this is particularly true for the cruise-ship case, where the ship normally sails at

14 kn but is expected to allow sailing at 21 kn, thus explaining the relatively large difference in total installed power.

In the case of the cruise ship, gas engines dominate in the cost-optimal scenarios, as they are the cheapest to install. With decreasing operating costs, they are first substituted by the MS-GEs, until a switching point where the SOFC starts to be installed instead of the MS-GE. The base concept is that the most efficient energy conversion unit (the MS-GE or the SOFC depending on the scenario) is used for base-load and the HS-GE for peaks. This can be also seen in Figure 8; in spite of the installed power of more than 10 MW, the HS-GE are only providing a minor contribution to the total power share in most scenarios from medium to low total GHG emissions.

In the case of the cruise ship, it is interesting to notice an additional shift when GHG emissions are reduced by more than 30% with respect to the unconstrained solution: in this case, it can be seen that: i. much of the HS-GE installed power is substituted by the MS-GE, to further reduce emissions at the expense of a higher investment cost; ii. the SOFC installed size further increases; iii. the optimal solution requires the installation of a battery, which allows storing the excess electric energy converted by the SOFC when the electric power demand is lower than the SOFC's minimum load.

In the case of the tanker, instead, the HS-DE is chosen instead of the HS-GE, and the Pareto front becomes a trade-off between SOFC, MS-GE and MS-DE: the SOFC is the most expensive to install, but also the one with the lowest GHG emissions. The MS-GE is the best from an economic perspective because it uses LNG, that is assumed to be cheaper than MDO, but the effects of methane slip makes it environmentally worse than Diesel engines. Once again, the HS engine is chosen mostly for peaks of power demand (in the case of the tanker, for the high-speed voyage), and hence has little contribution to the overall energy share (see Fig. 8).

Figure 9 shows the expected yearly emissions from the different solutions on the Pareto front, showing the effect of the higher share of SOFC use not only on GHGs, but also on NO_x and CO. It can be seen that the benefit of shifting towards SOFCs goes beyond the gains in terms of GHG emissions: All other emissions are also reduced, going practically to zero for the lowest GHG emissions scenarios. By observing Figure 9 together with 8 it can also be seen the high importance of the methane-slip phenomenon, and how much it influences the type of solutions present on the Pareto-front: while CO_2 emissions are only reduced by a maximum of approximately 20% by shifting to an SOFC-based power plant, GHG emissions are reduced by almost twice as much (approximately 35%). This is due to the high impact of methane slip on GHG emissions from gas engines. It appears as a consequence that, while a solution entirely based on gas engines would be optimal from a cost perspective, this would not be necessarily the case from an environmental one.

(a) Cruise ship

(b) Tanker

Figure 7. Results of the multi-objective optimization: Installed sizes of the main components. All values are expressed in terms of installed power [MW], save for the battery, that is represented in terms of installed capacity [MWh].

4.2 Sensitivity analysis

The two-step GSA as described in Section 2.2 was applied to the two case studies. In both cases, the MOO problem was modified into a single-objective optimization problem by dropping the environmental objective, and only retaining the cost-related one, with no constraint on the emissions. The Morris screening was applied to the 65 uncertain parameters with settings $r = 50$ trajectories and $p = 4$ levels. Two main optimization variables were selected as outputs of interest: the installed capacity of the SOFC unit ($P_{\text{SOFC}}^{\text{inst}}$), and the total annualized cost ($C_{\text{tot,ann}}$).

The results of the analysis are shown in Fig. 10 for the

Figure 8. Results of the multi-objective optimization: Cumulative contribution to the total electric demand (propulsion and auxiliary) from each technology.

most relevant parameters, selected based on having a sensitivity value higher than 5% of the maximum value for at least one of the two variables of interest. Each of the two outputs is represented as percentage of the maximum value with respect to j -th output of interest.

The application of the screening allows reducing the space to explore with a more detailed sensitivity analysis. 16 out of the 65 uncertain parameters were selected for further analysis. The results highlight the importance of cost-related parameters on the installation decision, as expected: all cost-related parameters (the lifetime of the stack, and the specific investment cost of the SOFC parts) are all included among the most relevant parameters that are selected in the screening stage. It is interesting to notice how the screening confirms the importance of including in the model the impact of the cost of lost weight and volume: this is shown by the selection of related parameters (cost of lost volume and weight, power density) among the variables retained by the Morris screening in both the cruise ship and tanker cases.

The comparison of the two case studies shows that the Morris screening identifies as significant mostly the same

Figure 9. Results of the multi-objective optimization: Pollutant emissions.

variables, with few exceptions. The screening performed in the first phase of the GSA allowed applying the global sensitivity analysis as described in Section 2.2 on a more limited number of parameters.

The results of the application of the Sobol method for GSA are presented in Figure 11a for the cruise ship and in Figure 11b for the tanker. In each of the two figures, the plot on the left refers the normalized sensitivity of the SOFC installed power, while the one on the right to the normalized sensitivity of the total annualized cost. For each parameter, two sensitivity values are presented:

- The **first-order sensitivity** (S_1) shows the "main" sensitivity of the selected output to the specific uncertain parameter, that is defined as the ratio between the reduction of the expected value of the output variance when fixing the i -th parameter to its nominal value (all other parameters are varying), and the total variance of the output.

(a) Cruise ship

(b) Tanker

Figure 10. Results of parameter screening phase of the GSA

- The **total-effect sensitivity** (S_T) is an index that attempts to provide an estimate of the total effect of the specific uncertain parameter on the output of interest. S_T thereby includes not only the effects of the i -th param-

(a) Cruise ship

(b) Tanker

Figure 11. Results of the parameter prioritization phase of the GSA

eter alone, but also the combined effects of several uncertain parameters.

Quite consistently, the application of variance-based methods substantially confirms the results of the Morris screening.

As expected, the most relevant parameters for the installed SOFC size are cost-related parameters. It should be noted, however, that apparently the very first in the ranking is the lifetime of the stacks. This is also related to the assumptions for the bounds of the uncertainty range for this parameter (between 3 and 8 years, with a reference value of 6), but it clearly points out the relevance of this parameter. The relevance of the fuel cost is also significant: higher fuel prices will make it more significant to install efficient, but expensive, technologies. The efficiency of the SOFC comes only in fourth place, together with the efficiency of the MS-GE: the two technologies are almost mutually exclusive, and as the respective efficiency shift, the installed sizes are also expected to follow. It should be noted, however, that the first-order sensitivity to these parameters is much lower than the total one. This can be explained by the fact that these parameters actively influence the installed size of the SOFC mostly in combination with other parameters, rather than directly.

As expected, also parameters influencing operational costs have a relatively large impact on the optimal decision. This can be seen by the presence of both the LNG fuel cost and of the carbon tax rate high in the list, together with the efficiency of the SOFC. The LNG cost and carbon tax rate act in the exact same way: by proportionally increasing their respective values, operational costs increase, thus making it more convenient to install the energy conversion units that feature the highest conversion efficiency (in this case, the SOFC).

The results are very similar for the two case studies, with the exception of the relevance of the cost of lost volume/weight, which appears to be more relevant in the cruise ship case compared to the tanker case. This can be explained by the fact that the power-to-volume ratio of SOFCs is worse than their power-to-weight ratio, especially when compared to internal combustion engines.

Based on the previous results, the uncertain parameters that showed to have the highest impact on the installed size of the SOFC were investigated with additional detail: the specific investment cost and lifetime of the SOFC, and the price of LNG. It should be noted that, while they are in reality different parameters, the SOFC specific investment cost parameters and the SOFC lifetime build together to one annualized specific cost investment parameter, as shown in Eq. 3. Assuming to only focus on the uncertainty on the lifetime of the SOFC stack, and that the specific investment cost of the stack and of the system behave according to a similar pattern (defined by a common uncertain parameter ranging from 0 to 1, where 0 corresponds to the lower bound and 1 to the upper bound), Figure 12a shows how the annualized specific cost investment depends on these parameters. The sensitivity of the SOFC installed size on the annualized specific cost investment and on the LNG price is shown in Figure 12b. It appears clearly that while the LNG price also has a role, the reduction of the annualized specific cost investment is the main parameter that makes a difference in the optimizer's decision of whether it is cost optimal to install a large SOFC on board, or not.

This reinforces the previous observation related to the high difference between S_T and S_I for the c_{LNG} parameter.

5. Discussion

5.1 Results discussion

The results of this paper show that SOFCs could potentially become an important technology for future ship power plants, if there will be an additional drive towards reducing GHG emissions. This paper showed that by means of changing the main energy conversion unit on board from conventional ICEs to SOFCs the gain in terms of GHG emissions could reach up to 34%. This confirms the results of previous studies, where the use of SOFCs was associated to significant energy savings (e.g. 50% savings in [24]). The side-effect of dramatically reducing emissions of other pollutants, such as NO_x and CO, also contributes to the environmental advantages of a wider adoption of fuel cells in shipping.

However, the results also allowed to show that, as of today, SOFCs would not be selected as part of a cost-optimal solution, in spite of their higher conversion efficiency. This comes as the consequence of their relatively high investment cost, in conjunction with the expected low lifetime of the fuel cell stacks. These results were also studied from the perspective of the influence of the uncertainty on a number of different parameters, and showed that high-uncertain cost-related parameters, in particular the specific investment cost of the SOFC, the lifetime of the stack, and the cost of fuel have a high impact on the optimal installed size of the SOFC. Given the positive expected impact on the environment from a wider adoption of SOFCs as prime mover on board ships, this suggests that policy makers should focus on decreasing the investment cost gap by focusing on the up-scaling of the production processes. On the other hand, while the higher electrical efficiency of SOFCs suggests that they would benefit from higher fuel prices or from policies with similar effects (such as a carbon tax), this effect is relatively smaller. It should also be noted that, as pointed out in earlier studies, low-investment energy-efficient technologies with low pay-back times are generally favored over solutions with a higher initial cost, regardless of the long-term benefits [21].

The results also highlight the importance of one of the main limitations still existing today to the use of SOFCs in transport applications: their limited dynamic abilities. This is shown, in this study, by the relatively high importance that the only load-related parameter that was included in the study: the minimum load at which the fuel cell can be operated, which resulted of high importance in the case of the merchant vessel. It should be noted, however, that while the assumption of the existence of a minimum operating load allowed to account for this limitation, this is far from the most accurate way of representing this characteristic. For instance, SOFCs can, in principle, idle while burning a limited amount of fuel to maintain the temperature for a faster start-up; also, recent developments for mobile SOFCs applications have allowed reducing the start-up time; finally, the present optimization

(a) SOFC specific annualized cost [EUR/kW] as a function of the stack lifetime and of the relative specific investment cost of SOFC stack and system

(b) Cost-optimal installed SOFC power [kW] as a function of the SOFC specific annualized cost and of the LNG price.

Figure 12. Parametric analysis of SOFC investment decision

setup did not allow for considering the existence of several SOFC units: while the linearity of the formulation of costs and fuel consumption prevents this from having any influence on the results, the same is not true for the load limitation. This suggests that this specific aspect should be taken into account with additional details in future studies.

This high uncertainty casts a different light on future optimization-based studies for the analysis of the potential of fuel cell technologies in shipping. The importance of performing a sensitivity analysis for this type of results was also highlighted in previous studies [77], but up to date most optimization studies of ship energy systems, also when cost optimization is involved, do not include a GSA. The uncertainty on these parameters plays an important role in the optimization results, going beyond that introduced by, for instance, model linearization. Future optimization studies should focus on using uncertainty-based optimization methods, such as the one proposed by [54].

It should also be noted that the results here presented in terms of emissions are largely influenced by the methane slip measured in marine gas engines [74]. Based on these emission factors, as of today, gas engines have a higher impact on the climate than traditional Diesel engines. While this is not the main focus of this paper, this is an observation that should lead policy makers not to overlook this aspect (as of today, the only regulation for GHG emissions in shipping is the EEDI, that takes into account the lower CO₂ emissions from gas engines due to the lower carbon content, but does not account for the methane slip). Future policies should explicitly include all GHG emissions, so as to either drive towards a more effective reduction of CH₄ emissions from gas engines, or to provide an additional driver towards switching to other, more environmental friendly technologies, such as fuel cells. The results of the sensitivity analysis highlighted the large impact of the uncertainty of the value of a potential carbon tax rate as one of the most significant for the decision of the installation of a SOFC as energy conversion unit. While the uncertainty on fuel prices is aleatory, and hence impossible to reduce, that on the price of carbon is decided by the relevant institutions, that have thus a clear possibility to drive the shipping sector towards higher sustainability.

5.2 Future work

To reduce the computational time of each optimization, a necessary step when applying a GSA, an MILP approach was used. This choice, compared to the widespread use of non-linear approaches (see, among others, [77, 28, 5]) generates an inevitable loss in accuracy. In particular, the effect of off-design performance of both ICEs and SOFCs was neglected, with efficiencies, temperatures and flows assumed to be constant over the entire operational range. It has been proven that a nonlinear approach can lead to better results in terms of load-allocation [5, 28]. Similarly, the linearization of the costs also include a loss in accuracy, due to missing to model the effects of the scale. Both these aspects should be investigated

further in future studies, comparing the findings of this paper with the results of the application of a nonlinear approach. As observed in the previous section, however, the uncertainty in the results of this study, connected to the large uncertainty on many problem parameters, is significantly larger than the accuracy loss related to using an MILP approach instead of a MINLP one.

While SOFC technology is rapidly developing, it is still the case that these units generally have poor dynamic behavior. In this study, this was accounted for by forcing SOFC units to be kept running at all times, thus addressing the limitation of long startup times. Future studies should also take into account the limitations in terms of load-following behavior: in real applications, energy storage devices might be required to compensate for too rapid power fluctuations, and this should be accounted for in the optimization problem.

This study also worked on the assumption of using an AC power grid on board of the ship. If SOFCs are to become the main energy conversion unit, the fact that both SOFCs and batteries generate in DC, together with the known advantages in terms of regulating rotating machines (such as pumps and compressors) by means of frequency converters [86], the result could be further improved by assuming a DC power grid instead.

Finally, there is an unexplored potential in terms of a better integration of the SOFC thermal systems with the rest of the ship. In this study, aiming at keeping a pragmatic approach, the SOFCs is assumed to be used as "stand-alone" boxes with given inputs and outputs of fuel, electric power, and heat. In reality, however, the internal heat balance of a SOFC system can be shifted based on the main focus of the system, on the costs of the heat exchanger network, and on other design and operational parameters. The SOFC technology used in this study can work at a 53% electrical efficiency and 27% thermal efficiency, well-suited for cogeneration purposes. Other SOFC-based cogeneration units have shown to be able to operate at higher electrical efficiency, but with lower thermal output, and at lower temperature. Future studies should focus on estimating how the detailed optimization of the balance-of-plant of the SOFC can influence the overall efficiency of the system, thus helping future naval architects and fuel cell developers in making the right design choices.

6. Conclusion

This paper presents the results of the optimization of a ship propulsion plant using solid oxide fuel cells as the main energy conversion device for the generation of electric power and heat on board.

The results of this study showed that the proposed system can achieve substantially higher performance compared to the baseline, with the potential of reducing GHG emissions by up to 34%. The results also showed that, in order to achieve significant reductions in GHG emission, SOFCs are the most cost-optimal solution when using natural gas as fuel. The increase in total cost coming from a larger SOFC installed

on board can go up to 33% higher in the case of the cruise ship and 43% higher in the case of the tanker. The case of the cruise ship, given its more regular operational profile, seems to be more suitable for a profitable installation of such systems, also given their additional advantages of reducing noise and vibrations.

The optimization problem was also analyzed in terms of its sensitivity to the uncertainty of various problem parameters. This operation highlighted that the high uncertainty on cost-related parameters for the SOFC makes a dramatic difference in terms of cost-optimality. This observation leads to the conclusions that future similar studies will need to take uncertainty into account, given its high impact on the optimal solution. In addition, from a practical perspective, the identified high relevance of parameters related to the investment cost of SOFCs suggests the importance on focusing on abating production costs, if a wider adoption of this technology in shipping is to be expected in the future.

Acknowledgments

The work of FB is financed by the European Commission with a H2020-MSCA-IF-EF grant (grant number 708288). We would like to thank Antti Pohjoranta from VTT for the fruitful discussions about the practical implications of the use of fuel cells on board of ships, and Mar Perez-Fortes, Ligang Wang and Jan van Herle for the discussions related to SOFCs, their potential, and their modelling.

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